

D6.3: IPR management plan

Project full title	Innovative Al filler Wires for Aircraft Structure
Project acronym	IAWAS
Topic / Call	JTI-CS2-2017-CfP07-AIR-01-34
Grant Agreement no.	821371
Start Date	02/10/2018
Duration	36 months
Version number	01.0
Due date	31/03/2019
Submission Date	08/04/2018

DISSEMINATION LEVEL		
PU	Public	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>

CHANGE CONTROL

Date	Version	Author (Company)	Changes to document
25/03/2019	v01.0	SONACA	Initial version
27/03/2019	V01.1	UAC	Inputs from CU
08/04/2019	V01.2	Selectarc	Inputs from Selectarc
08/04/2019	V01.3	Cranfield University	Inputs from UAC
04/06/2019	V01.4	IK4 LORTEK	Revised by Topic Manager
13/06/2019	V01.5	SONACA	Implementation of comments
17/06/2019	V01.6	IK4 LORTEK	Approved

INDEX

CHANGE CONTROL.....	2
INDEX	3
1. Introduction:.....	4
2. IPR management	4
2.1 GA extract	5
3. Agreement on Background.....	10
3.1 SONACA background:.....	10
3.2 UAC background:	12
3.3 Selectarc Welding background:.....	16
3.4 Cranfield university background:.....	18

1. Introduction:

This deliverable aims at gathering the information related to the Intellectual Property Right (IPR) management.

The recently signed Grant Agreement (GA): "GRANT AGREEMENT FOR PARTNERS NUMBER 821371 ITD/IADP/TA — GAM AIR 2018 PROJECT TITLE — IAWAS" already contains the rules to be followed.

The IPR strategy also includes a collection of the background IP brought to the project in paragraph 3 of this document.

2. IPR management

The process for management of new intellectual property generated during the course of our project is governed by the Consortium Agreement and Implementation Agreement, which ensures fair exploitation rights for all partners. The GA extract describing the main rules is in the next sub-paragraph.

Any new IP will be the property of the partner responsible for its development with access beyond the project being under fair and reasonable conditions (or as agreed by partners and the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking).

The basis of the IPR strategy is to allow the new scientific knowledge created by the project to be actively disseminated amongst academic communities to validate it and industrial communities to take it up. However, prior to the programme of dissemination activities, the partners will study the feasibility to patent the technological capabilities developed and the product, process or system applications. Hence, the full range of scientific, technological and product or system specific dissemination activities can be enabled without compromising the protection of the foreground IPR.

2.1 GA extract

SECTION 3 RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS RELATED TO BACKGROUND AND RESULTS

SUBSECTION 1 GENERAL

ARTICLE 23a — MANAGEMENT OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

23a.1 Obligation to take measures to implement the Commission Recommendation on the management of intellectual property in knowledge transfer activities

Beneficiaries that are universities or other public research organisations must take measures to implement the principles set out in Points 1 and 2 of the Code of Practice annexed to the Commission Recommendation on the management of intellectual property in knowledge transfer activities²².

This does not change the obligations set out in Subsections 2 and 3 of this Section.

The beneficiaries must ensure that researchers and third parties involved in the action are aware of them.

23a.2 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches its obligations under this Article, the JU may apply any of the measures described in Chapter 6.

SUBSECTION 2 RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS RELATED TO BACKGROUND

²² Commission Recommendation C(2008) 1329 of 10.4.2008 on the management of intellectual property in knowledge transfer activities and the Code of Practice for universities and other public research institutions attached to this recommendation.

ARTICLE 24 — AGREEMENT ON BACKGROUND

24.1 Agreement on background

The beneficiaries must identify and agree (in writing) on the background for the action (**‘agreement on background’**).

‘Background’ means any data, know-how or information — whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights — that:

- (a) is held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement, and
- (b) is needed to implement the action or exploit the results.

24.2 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 43).

Such breaches may also lead to any of the other measures described in Chapter 6.

ARTICLE 25 — ACCESS RIGHTS TO BACKGROUND

25.1 Exercise of access rights — Waiving of access rights — No sub-licensing

To exercise access rights, this must first be requested in writing (**‘request for access’**).

‘Access rights’ means rights to use results or background under the terms and conditions laid down in this Agreement.

Waivers of access rights are not valid unless in writing.

Unless agreed otherwise, access rights do not include the right to sub-license.

25.2 Access rights for other beneficiaries, for implementing their own tasks under the action

The beneficiaries must give each other access — on a royalty-free basis — to background needed to implement their own tasks under the action, unless the beneficiary that holds the background has — before acceding to the Agreement —:

- (a) informed the other beneficiaries that access to its background is subject to legal restrictions or limits, including those imposed by the rights of third parties (including personnel), or
- (b) agreed with the other beneficiaries that access would not be on a royalty-free basis.

25.3 Access rights for other beneficiaries, for exploiting their own results

The beneficiaries must give each other access — under fair and reasonable conditions — to background needed for exploiting their own results, unless the beneficiary that holds the background has — before acceding to the Agreement — informed the other beneficiaries that access to its background is subject to legal restrictions or limits, including those imposed by the rights of third parties (including personnel).

‘**Fair and reasonable conditions**’ means appropriate conditions, including possible financial terms or royalty-free conditions, taking into account the specific circumstances of the request for access, for example the actual or potential value of the results or background to which access is requested and/or the scope, duration or other characteristics of the exploitation envisaged.

Requests for access may be made — unless agreed otherwise — up to one year after the period set out in Article 3.

25.4 Access rights for affiliated entities

Unless otherwise agreed in the consortium agreement, access to background must also be given — under fair and reasonable conditions (see above; Article 25.3) and unless it is subject to legal restrictions or limits, including those imposed by the rights of third parties (including personnel) — to affiliated entities²³ established in an EU Member State or ‘**associated country**’²⁴, if this is needed to exploit the results generated by the beneficiaries to which they are affiliated.

Unless agreed otherwise (see above; Article 25.1), the affiliated entity concerned must make the request directly to the beneficiary that holds the background.

Requests for access may be made — unless agreed otherwise — up to one year after the period set out in Article 3.

25.5 Access rights for third parties

The beneficiaries must, under the conditions set out in Article 25.2 and Article 25.3, give access to their background to the complementary beneficiary²⁵ that is the topic manager²⁶.

25.6 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 43).

²³ For the definition see Article 2.1(2) Rules for Participation Regulation No 1290/2013: ‘**affiliated entity**’ means any legal entity that is:

- under the direct or indirect control of a participant, or
- under the same direct or indirect control as the participant, or
- directly or indirectly controlling a participant.

‘Control’ may take any of the following forms:

- (a) the direct or indirect holding of more than 50% of the nominal value of the issued share capital in the legal entity concerned, or of a majority of the voting rights of the shareholders or associates of that entity;
- (b) the direct or indirect holding, in fact or in law, of decision-making powers in the legal entity concerned.

However the following relationships between legal entities shall not in themselves be deemed to constitute controlling relationships:

- (a) the same public investment corporation, institutional investor or venture-capital company has a direct or indirect holding of more than 50% of the nominal value of the issued share capital or a majority of voting rights of the shareholders or associates;
- (b) the legal entities concerned are owned or supervised by the same public body.

²⁴ For the definition, see Article 2.1(3) of the Rules for Participation Regulation No 1290/2013: ‘**associated country**’ means a third country which is party to an international agreement with the Union, as identified in Article 7 of Horizon 2020 Framework Programme Regulation No 1291/2013. Article 7 sets out the conditions for association of non-EU countries to Horizon 2020.

²⁵ ‘**Complementary beneficiary**’ means a beneficiary of the complementary grant agreement.

²⁶ The beneficiaries shall enjoy equivalent access rights to the results generated by the topic manager which shall be set out in the complementary grant agreement.

Such breaches may also lead to any of the other measures described in Chapter 6.

SUBSECTION 3 RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS RELATED TO RESULTS

ARTICLE 26 — OWNERSHIP OF RESULTS

26.1 Ownership by the beneficiary that generates the results

Results are owned by the beneficiary that generates them.

‘Results’ means any (tangible or intangible) output of the action such as data, knowledge or information — whatever its form or nature, whether it can be protected or not — that is generated in the action, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.

26.2 Joint ownership by several beneficiaries

Two or more beneficiaries own results jointly if:

- (a) they have jointly generated them and
- (b) it is not possible to:
 - (i) establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary, or
 - (ii) separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining their protection (see Article 27).

The joint owners must agree (in writing) on the allocation and terms of exercise of their joint ownership (‘**joint ownership agreement**’), to ensure compliance with their obligations under this Agreement.

Unless otherwise agreed in the joint ownership agreement, each joint owner may grant non-exclusive licences to third parties to exploit jointly-owned results (without any right to sub-license), if the other joint owners are given:

- (a) at least 45 days advance notice and
- (b) fair and reasonable compensation.

Once the results have been generated, joint owners may agree (in writing) to apply another regime than joint ownership (such as, for instance, transfer to a single owner (see Article 30) with access rights for the others).

26.3 Rights of third parties (including personnel)

If third parties (including personnel) may claim rights to the results, the beneficiary concerned must ensure that it complies with its obligations under the Agreement.

If a third party generates results, the beneficiary concerned must obtain all necessary rights (transfer, licences or other) from the third party, in order to be able to respect its obligations as if those results were generated by the beneficiary itself.

If obtaining the rights is impossible, the beneficiary must refrain from using the third party to generate the results.

26.4 JU ownership, to protect results

26.4.1 The JU may — with the consent of the beneficiary concerned — assume ownership of results to protect them, if a beneficiary intends — up to four years after the period set out in Article 3 — to disseminate its results without protecting them, except in any of the following cases:

- (a) the lack of protection is because protecting the results is not possible, reasonable or justified (given the circumstances);
- (b) the lack of protection is because there is a lack of potential for commercial or industrial exploitation, or
- (c) the beneficiary intends to transfer the results to another beneficiary or third party established in an EU Member State or associated country, which will protect them.

Before the results are disseminated and unless any of the cases above under Points (a), (b) or (c) applies, the beneficiary must formally notify the JU and at the same time inform it of any reasons for refusing consent. The beneficiary may refuse consent only if it can show that its legitimate interests would suffer significant harm.

If the JU decides to assume ownership, it will formally notify the beneficiary concerned within 45 days of receiving notification.

No dissemination relating to these results may take place before the end of this period or, if the JU takes a positive decision, until it has taken the necessary steps to protect the results.

26.4.2 The JU may — with the consent of the beneficiary concerned — assume ownership of results to protect them, if a beneficiary intends — up to four years after the period set out in Article 3 — to stop protecting them or not to seek an extension of protection, except in any of the following cases:

- (a) the protection is stopped because of a lack of potential for commercial or industrial exploitation;
- (b) an extension would not be justified given the circumstances.

A beneficiary that intends to stop protecting results or not seek an extension must — unless any of the cases above under Points (a) or (b) applies — formally notify the JU at least 60 days before the protection lapses or its extension is no longer possible and at the same time inform it of any reasons for refusing consent. The beneficiary may refuse consent only if it can show that its legitimate interests would suffer significant harm.

If the JU decides to assume ownership, it will formally notify the beneficiary concerned within 45 days of receiving notification.

26.5 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 43).

Such breaches may also lead to the any of the other measures described in Chapter 6.

3. Agreement on Background

3.1 SONACA background:

For more than 40 years, SONACA stress office has acquired a solid experience in the structural analysis of both metallic and composite aerostructures, from concept to certification, as risk sharing partner of Airbus, Embraer, Bombardier, DASSAULT and Pilatus.

Our stress engineers are responsible for all kind of structural analysis required to obtain FAA and EASA certification, including finite element and classical analyses to establish interface loads with adjacent structures, detailed static stressing, dynamic, impact, fatigue, damage tolerance and test correlation analyses.

The structural justification activities are strongly supported by a numerical background based upon university and software editor links.

These applications have been performed in an in-house platform (SONIA) that is an original concept addressing the full sizing chain and embedding best in-class solvers (CATIA, SIMCENTER, SAMCEF, NASTRAN, ABAQUS, FLUENT and in-house tools).

SONACA Virtual Testing concepts have been proven on many AC projects for more than 15 years and are continuously developed through R&T projects (composite optimization, composite damage, 3DPrinting, icing tool improvements, ...). Thanks to this environment, advanced modelling is standardly used in an easy and robust way (capitalization & automation).

Global objectives are to provide higher added value to our customers:

- By proposing innovative design by virtual exploration
- By being capable to overcome actively very complex engineering subjects
- By going towards more digital certification under certain conditions (bird impact on metallic FLE for example)
- And by addressing QCP aspects: mass (\downarrow conservatisms), costs (NRC & RC), lead times, risks

Topology and parametric optimization in conjunction with traditional manufacturing are used at SONACA since several years in order to save mass while maximizing the part stiffness's.

Figure 1 Topology and parametric optimization

With the arrival of the AM process for metallic part, the interest for topology optimization is tenfold because of the high freedom in shape offered by this process. The merge of topology optimization and AM process give the opportunity to use efficiently the material by highlighting the loading paths and allowing designing a part with the lowest mass while maximizing her

stiffness in regards to the loading conditions. Another task of parametric optimization is generally supporting the topology optimization in order to define the shell thickness or truss/bars sections while respecting mechanical constraints such as VON MISES criterion for example.

Spatial fitting
 In development
 Topology optimization
 (study realized by SAMTECH with
 TOPOL in the frame of FASAMA)

Figure 2 Topology and parametric optimization in AM – Spatial fitting

The topology optimizer used at SONACA is TOPOL which is part of the SIEMENS suite.

When the part could be studied in standalone, Inspire from Altair could also be used to have a quick overview of what could be the optimized shape.

Boss Quattro which is also part of the Siemens suite is used for parametric optimization.

SONACA is actively working on the numerical tools for Additive manufacturing through R&D projects such as FASAMA and a new GSTP project called “DESIGN4AM”, won in the end of 2018 in collaboration with SIEMENS consisting in the development of numerical methods for additive manufacturing design. From topology optimization, to sizing up to CAD reconstruction and Additive manufacturing process simulation, the goal of this work is to reduce rework design activities by taking into account very soon in the design phase manufacturing constraints (amount of supports, overhangs, holes to be supported ...etc). It respects mechanical constraints on the part and tends to avoid printing errors due to thermal stresses by performing process simulation before manufacturing.

Figure 3 Evolution in a part design thanks to AM and topology optimisation

3.2 UAC background:

UAC can support casting, extrusion, machining, surface treatment, kitting, and assembly activities. UAC offers a full range of alloys and tempers and their in-house R&D group can also develop advanced alloys tailored for specific applications in order to help find the right balance of strength, damage tolerance, and corrosion resistance. From the talented people running their extrusion presses to the experienced Metallurgists and Production Engineers, UAC people are dedicated to constant improvement in both their product and their process.

Throughout the three available mills, UAC offers:

- Casthouse able to cast various log diameters.
- Lab scale casting equipment.
- Optical spectrometer.
- Homogenisation furnace.
- Billet scalper.
- 18 presses ranging from 170 to 16 200 tons.
- Container sizes from 2,5 inches diameter to 29 inches diameter.
- Maximum T-temper length of 104 feet, produced in a wide variety of alloy/temper combinations.
- Vertical and horizontal solution heat-treat furnaces, stretchers for stress relieving and straightening.
- Roll straightening machines and shape correcting draw benches.
- Annealing and age ovens.
- Ultrasonic inspection tanks up to 110 feet in length.
- Complete laboratory capability:
 - Universal tensile/compression testing machine.
 - Hardness.
 - Flare test.
 - Bearing resistance.
 - Macro and micrographs.
 - Fracture toughness.
 - Fatigue & Fatigue crack growth.
 - Corrosion tests such as EXCO, SCC, IGC.
 - SEM is also possible thanks to partnership with Universities.
- Tool and dies shops with CNC and EDM capability

UAC also offers machining, surface treatment, kitting, and assembly services such as:

- State-of-the-art high-speed CNC five-axis machining centres producing extrusion profile and plate engineered components.
- Machining of extruded profiles from cleats through 10m seat tracks.
- Anodizing TSA and SAA future BSA.
- Penetrant testing.
- Automated 12m anodizing line providing REACH-compliant and environmentally friendly, chromefree solutions.
- Sealing, painting, and part-marking operations for all OEMs.
- Climate-controlled assembly of products like floor and cargo ramp structures, floor beams, wing cleat kitting.

Recent alloy developments done by UAC:

UAC has developed Ag-free AA2043 alloy, which has a low Copper/Lithium ratio. This alloy has a very low density of 2,63g/cc in comparison with legacy AA7175 T79511 alloy (density of 2,81g/cc) which has similar static properties.

Figure 4: TEM image of AA2043 T85 alloy

Figure 4 shows that AA2043 T85 is chiefly strengthened by T1 precipitates (streaks on the picture). In the TEM area observed by analysing the diffraction pattern the T1 phases are predominant in comparison with δ' and θ' which are less visible. This prevalence of T1 precipitates led UAC to a good combination of strength and fracture toughness thanks to careful compositional and process control.

Following charts presents the excellent properties achieved with the good balance between toughness and static properties despite the low Copper/Lithium ratio.

Figure 5: Fracture toughness obtained on extruded crossbeam in various positions and directions

Figure 6: Tensile properties in longitudinal direction in various area and thickness of an extruded crossbeam

Figure 7: Tensile properties in Transversal direction in various area and thickness of an extruded crossbeam

Figure 8: Elongation in Longitudinal and Transversal direction in various area and thickness of an extruded crossbeam

UAC has also recently developed AA2395 (density 2,68g/cc). This aluminium lithium alloy is similar to AA2195 in composition with a higher Copper/Lithium ratio and contains Ag which main be beneficial for weldability and strengthening.

Figure 9: High Copper/Lithium ratio AA2395

This alloy has very high static properties, comparable to the very high Zn containing alloys such as AA7136, but with much better corrosion properties. Several optimisations have been necessary to improve in particular its formability. The illustration below show how a severe local forming like joggling has been possible thanks to an optimal compositional and process control.

2395-T84 Jogging Trials

Figure 10: Jogging trials on AA2395 T84 alloy

AA2395 will be used as reference for starting this study for the reasons explained the part one. AA2395 was chosen as one of the first two alloys to be tested in the first step of IAWAS, LBW and WAAM activities will be performed.

3.3 Selectarc Welding background:

Selectarc Welding, manufacturer of welding and brazing consumables is going to be in charge of the wire drawing of the wire. Additional support can be provided related with the following services:

1. R&D: at the heart of their factories. A team of experienced technicians, led by metallurgical engineers (for both welding and brazing), reviews our customers' requests, develops and manufactures new products, and improves the process to better meet their requirements.
2. Customer services and technical advice: with 60 years of experience, the FSH WELDING GROUP stands out by its ability to respond to highly technical specific markets for advanced industries. Their technical sales teams and engineers are at customer's disposal to find effective solutions and the means to implement for specific applications or to improve customers manufacturing processes.
3. Customizing on demand: The Group's strengths include responsiveness and flexibility including: formulas, shapes, packaging, labels and markings.
4. Custom Work: the FSH WELDING GROUP strives to enable its customers to benefit from its broad know-how. In situations where the work is precise and complex, they are able to offer a service that meets all their customer's requirements, even the most specific.

On-demand work:

- Straightening: all categories from $\varnothing 6$ to $\varnothing 0,3$ mm.
 - Spooling: on D300, D200, D100, K400, K500, SD400 special coils...
 - Drawing: from $\varnothing 5,5$ down to $\varnothing 0,3$ on steels, stainless steels, nickel base, coppers, aluminium, cobalt base...
 - Pickling: chemical and mechanical.
 - Pre-forming.
 - Marking: sizing and flagging.
 - Packaging.
 - Heat treatment: Ar, H2, Air.
5. Training & Lectures: Engineers and technicians are at their customers disposal to share their knowledge, either inter-or intra-company. Various welding and soldering training programs have been developed to meet the requirements of our customers. Their duration depends on the trainees' basic level and on the targeted objectives. Their specialists often contribute to international lectures, including: IIW 2011 (Chennai-India); NACE 2011 (Oman); BHEL 2010 (Trichy-India); IIW 2009 (Singapore); NWS-200/9 (Mumbai-India), IIW 2014 (Mumbai-India)

SELECTARC WELDING operational capacities

A total of 8400m² including 200m² for R&D Laboratory and 600m² for offices leads to a pole of welding excellence.

Figure 11: Selectarc Welding Grandvillars plant

Selectarc Welding has some facilities for extruding, drawing and spooling machines.

Figure 12: Selectarc Welding equipment

List of relevant equipment:

- Extrusions aluminium line.
- 5 drawing machines (2 specially dedicated for aluminium).
- Spooling machines.

Laboratory equipment:

- Welding Machine.
- Spectrometer, tensile test machine, impact test machine.
- Macrograph and micrograph inspections.
- Hardness measurements.

3.4 Cranfield university background:

Welding Engineering and Laser Processing Centre (WELPC) of Cranfield University will be working on this project. WELPC is in School of Aerospace, Transport and Manufacturing. It specialises in fundamental, strategic and applied research in the area of advanced fusion joining processes and high deposition rate additive built structures. The centre owns a 700m² laboratory with a variety of laser and arc welding facilities. These facilities are mostly equipped with robots and CNC machines to enable automated welding and additive manufacturing process. The laboratory also uses state-of-the-art quantitative analysis facilities to characterise and model welding and depositing processes necessary for fundamental analysis.

There are four main research areas in WELPC of Cranfield University, including:

- Additive Manufacturing
- Laser Processing
- Process modelling and residual stress engineering
- Novel joining solutions

Cranfield University operational capacities

WELPC at Cranfield University has a long experience in development of additive manufacturing for building of large parts for various industries. The WAAM (wire + arc additive manufacturing) process has attracted over 40 industrial and academic partners over the last ten years of running this program by the WELPC. Extensive researches has been / is being performed on various areas of the WAAM process, including process strategy development for complex features, thermal cycle based process control, process monitoring, WAAM software development, distortion and stress control, integrated cold work, etc. Many WAAM materials have been / are being studied, including low alloy steels (mild steel, high strength steel...), stainless steels, aluminium alloys, nickel alloys, refractory metals, and titanium alloys.

WELPC of Cranfield University has successfully built many WAAM parts for industrial partners. Open architecture systems are used for the WAAM process. Typical systems include a robot + rotational table or an open gantry system. As both of these systems are easily scaled, WAAM can potentially print parts with no limits in size. The major manufacturing facilities in WELPC and WAAM demonstration parts are shown in the following figures.

Figure 13: Main laboratory of WELPC Cranfield University (left), Multi-process flexible cell (right)

Figure 14: Large gantry CNC machine for WAAM process (left), Robotic deposition facility with argon enclosure (right)

Figure 15: Titanium frame structure by WAAM (left), Titanium thin wall structure by WAAM (right)

Figure 16: High strength wing structure, Weight efficient structure (right)

Cranfield University Engineering Facilities:

Facility name	Purpose	Resource statement
Robot + rotational table system	To provide motion for the WAAM process	Existing facility, provided by Cranfield University
CMT welding power source	To provide heat source for the WAAM process	Existing facility, provided by Cranfield University
Arc welding monitor	To record the instant current and voltages of arc welding in process study	Existing facility, provided by Cranfield University
Process monitoring camera	To record the process for process performance evaluation	Existing facility, provided by Cranfield University
Cutting machines	To cut substrates for experiments, and to cut samples for property analysis	Existing facility, provided by Cranfield University

Cranfield University Computer software:

Cranfield University IT department can provide licenses of various software for research purpose:

Software name	Purpose
Siemens NX	Cad model generating and editing
Microsoft software	Report writing
Matlab	Path planning for moving the manipulator
Rhinoceros 3d	Path planning for moving the manipulator

Cranfield University Testing capabilities:

Cranfield University has a metallurgy laboratory for performing microstructure analysis. The mechanical testing laboratory of Cranfield University has a number of servo-hydraulic and electro-mechanical testing machines in a wide range of loading capabilities.

Cranfield University Experience in WAAM projects:

WELPC of Cranfield University has successfully delivered and continuously working on many WAAM projects. The major ones are listed as following:

- GSTP - Primary Structures made by Additive Manufacturing (ESA, on-going): this project is to demonstrate the applicability of using Additive Manufacturing processes for highly loaded primary spacecraft and launcher structures. The main activities are as following:
 - Define the AM processes most suitable for spacecraft or launcher structures.
 - Perform testing on standard test specimens in order to obtain a full set of mechanical properties for a given material (aluminium alloy / titanium alloy) and a given AM process for which all parameters are defined and controlled during manufacturing.
 - Design and build 3 technology demonstrators (2 spacecraft structures, one launcher structure), two items of each.
 - Test the technology demonstrators under typical loading conditions.

- Additively Manufactured Ring for International Berthing Docking Mechanism (ESA, on-going): this project is to demonstrate the applicability of Additive Manufacturing processes for producing an optimised International Behring Docking Mechanism. The main activities for Cranfield University are as following:
 - Contribute to the design optimisation for the WAAM process.
 - Manufacturing of breadboard geometry, including process study for the optimised structure, decide the best manufacturing parameters, and produce the breadboard geometry.
 - Definition of test plan.
 - Manufacturing of complete ring using WAAM process, including tooling design based on FE distortion estimation.
 - Perform mechanical testing of samples (tensile test).
- WAAMMat Programme (on-going): to bring WAAM to a maturity level suitable for implementation in aerospace and other industry sectors a technology maturation programme, WAAMMat, is running with over 20 industrial partners. Major highlights are:
 - Path planning software that can assist path planning of complicated structures.
 - Control of multi-robots and multi external axis with coordinate motion.
 - New processes such as Cold Metal Transfer, multi wire MIG and high frequency TIG.
 - Out of chamber methods for all materials including titanium.
 - Use of process control algorithms to predict deposition geometry from input parameters.
 - Development of strategies for features such as enclosed sections, intersections and crossovers.
 - Control of microstructure using thermal and mechanical methods and chemical grain refinement.
 - Demonstration of integrated deposition and machining.
 - Many large scale industrial engineering structures have been produced.
- LASIMM Project (EU, on-going): large Additive Subtractive Integrated Modular Machine project is an EU project funded by H2020 program. The LASIMM project aim is to develop a large scale flexible hybrid additive / subtractive machine based on a modular architecture which is easily scalable. The major tasks for Cranfield University are:
 - To maximize deposition rates with larger diameter wires, multiple robots, and / or hybrid deposition processes.
 - To apply different cold working processes for improving material properties.
 - To develop measurement systems - incorporation of real time layer height monitoring and compensation methods.
 - To develop control system for the machine.
 - To investigate multi-material deposition - graded structure and dissimilar metals using friction surfacing.
- RoboWAAM Project (Innovate UK, ongoing): Robotic Wire + Arc Additive Manufacturing (RoboWAAM) project is funded by Innovate UK. The aim of this project is to develop a prototype intelligent WAAM system suitable for commercialisation with embedded process know-how that allows general users to automatically build large metallic parts. The major tasks for Cranfield University are:
 - Produce transportable WAAM cell suitable for Ti deposition.
 - Develop specialist hardware for Ti deposition (shielding and optimised plasma torches).
 - Incorporate process monitoring and control (layer height).
 - Develop control system and software.

- Investigate methods for in-process NDE.
- Build demonstrator parts.
- Study industrialisation of WAAM.
- 3D metal printer for International Space Station (ISS) - laser + wire with some severe restrictions (ESA, on-going): the aim of this project is to develop a prototype of AM machine that can be used in the international space station for depositing metals. The major tasks for Cranfield University are:
 - Select proper deposition process for depositing metal under the severe restrictions of ISS.
 - Simulate the deposition process with numerical models.
 - Design a deposition prototype machine.
 - Demonstrate the capability of this machine by building demonstrator parts.
- AMAZE Project (EU): Additive Manufacturing Aiming Towards Zero Waste & Efficient Production of High-Tech Metal Products (AMAZE) project is a project funded by EU 7th Framework Program. The overarching goal of AMAZE is to rapidly produce large defect-free additively-manufactured metallic components up to 2 metres in size, ideally with close to zero waste, for use in the following high-tech sectors namely: aeronautics, space, nuclear fusion, automotive and tooling. The major tasks for Cranfield University are:
 - Refractory metals.
 - Rolling of aluminium alloy and titanium alloy.
 - Global mechanical tensioning and cold work.
 - Demonstrator.
 - Topology optimisation.
 - Tensile and mechanical testing of ER70S.
- HiDepAM (EPSRC): High Deposition Rate Additive Manufacturing of Complex Metal Parts (HiDepAM) is funded by Engineering and Physical Science Research Council of UK. In this project Cranfield team is responsible on the following studies:
 - Out of position AM of titanium.
 - Layer shock penning.
 - Integrated rolling.
 - Integrated machining.
 - Online grain measurement.
- Wire and arc additive manufacturing of near net shapes for spacecraft propellant tanks (Innovate UK): Wire and arc additive manufacturing of near net shapes for spacecraft propellant tanks project is funded by Innovate UK. The main target of this project is to build the propellant tanks with WAAM process and achieve a near net shape, which minimize the machining. Main tasks include:
 - To demonstrate building large scale near net shapes of spacecraft propellant tanks with titanium alloy with WAAM process.
 - To demonstrate the final mechanical properties are comparable to the properties of forged parts.
 - To demonstrate a full manufacturing process including WAAM and machining for producing the propellant tanks.
 - To demonstrate the tank manufactured in this project meet the requirements of onerous ground and flight safety standards.
 - To perform cost analysis.
- Rawfeed project (Innovate UK): Rolling Assisted Wire Feed Direct Deposition for Production of High Value Aerospace Components (Rawfeed) project is funded by Innovate UK. The consortium are developing and validating the performance of the required sub-

system hardware and software to enable a wire feed additive manufacturing (AM) process utilising wire arc welding deposition combined with in-process rolling. Main tasks include:

- To integrate machine of WAAM and rolling.
- To integrate online monitoring system.
- To demonstrate building titanium alloy structures with the integrated machine.
- To demonstrate the integrated machine can provide titanium parts with acceptable performance for aerospace applications, while ensuring minimal distortion and high material utilisation efficiency.
- RUAM (EPSRC / IMRC Cranfield University): Ready-to-Use Additive Manufacturing (RUAM) project was an EPSRC funded project through the Cranfield Innovative Manufacturing Research Centre (IMRC). The main tasks of this project included:
 - Thermal-mechanical modelling of the wire+arc additive manufacturing process.
 - Process study of depositing steel and titanium alloys.
 - Design study of WAAM features.
 - Investigation of using interlayer rolling process to improve mechanical properties of deposited titanium alloy.
 - Investigation of integrated WAAM and machining process.

4. Foreground

The exploitable outputs of IAWAS are mainly the wires with the new compositions for WAAM and LBW applications.

Besides, knowledge in the following processes is going to be generated:

- WAAM of Al-Cu-Li alloys
- LBW of Al-Cu-Li alloys
- Casting, extrusion and wire drawing of Al-Cu-Li alloys